

IMPACT OF HYDROGEL AND MULCHING ON GROWTH AND GROWTH ATTRIBUTES OF MAIZE (*ZEA MAYS L.*) IN SANDY SOIL

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(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRONOMY)**Abstract**

An experiment was conducted to know the impact of hydrogel and mulching on growth and growth attributes of maize in sandy soil. Experimentation was laid out in randomised block design with two factors (hydrogel and mulching) with three levels each and one additional control. Different levels of hydrogel and types of mulches, their interactions and a control were analysed statistically. The results were shown that maximum plant height was recorded with main effects of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ at 30 DAS, rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at 30 and 60 DAS and their interaction at 30 DAS. The higher number of leaves (NL) plant⁻¹ was recorded with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at 60 and 90 DAS (14.31 and 10.71 respectively). Maximum leaf area (LA) was observed in main and interaction effects of hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at all the stages while it was on par with the treatments in which rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ with hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ at 60 DAS and with other two levels of hydrogel were applied at 90 DAS. Main and interaction effects of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum dry matter production (DMP) plant⁻¹ and root volume at harvest. When compare the control with treatments, control recorded the minimum plant height, NL, LA, DMP and root volume at harvest. Overall, application of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ combination with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ shown the higher growth than the other treatments and their combinations.

Key words – Hydrogel, mulch, rice straw, rice husk, coirpith compost

Introduction

Among the cereal crops, maize (*Zea mays L.*) is the third most key crop in India, after rice and wheat. In world, India's position is fourth in area, sixth in production, and tenth in productivity (2014). Among the states in India, Karnataka ranks first in area, while in case of production Tamil Nadu occupies first (DES, 2017).

Maize said to be water sensitive crop as excess and deficit water availability causes change in growth. Earlier research also proved that there is substantial proliferation in maize yields by the applying proper irrigation practices. sandy soils are known to be hold less water and normally prone to water scarcity. For improvement in growth of plants in sandy soil there is need to improve the moisture retentive capacity of sandy soil by adopting better management practices. Several agronomical practices like application of mulch and hydrogel can improve the water productivity by increase the temporal availability of water in the soil.

Hydrogel is a cross linked polymer made up of poly acrylamide which is hydrophilic in nature and degraded biologically. It absorbs the water several times than its original weight and absorbed water is made available to the crop by retaining it more time (Johnson and Veltkamp, 1985). Hydrogel application improved the existence rate of plants about 1.4 to 1.6 times higher with limited irrigation also. It improved the plant growth by enhancing the moisture retaining ability of soil and prolonging the wilting time at the time of moisture stress situation (Boatright *et al.*, 1997). Reduction in the plant height, LA, growth and yield of maize due to drought (Cattivelli *et al.*, 2008). Hydrogel maintained the proper soil moisture at both vegetative and reproductive growth stages of the maize crop and ultimately DMP and grain yield was improved (Dragicevic *et al.*, 2011). Fresh weight and root length of the maize was improved by the application of hydrogel especially in sandy soil (Mazen *et al.*, 2015).

Soil faced the water scarcity due to high evaporation under limited rainfall condition. To reduce evaporation mulching with locally available material was perfectly suitable. Mulching enhanced the Water Use Efficiency (Unger and Jones, 1981) by increased in dry matter accretion and dissemination in maize. Straw mulching may delay the leaf senescence and shows the high LA at later stages of maize crop (Tolk *et al.*, 1999). Hydrogel which is a fairly new technology, its use efficiency must be compared with mulch to study the influence of hydrogel and mulching on soil growth and growth attributes of maize in sandy soil.

Materials and Methods

A research programme was conducted at College of Agriculture, Padannakkad, Kerala Agricultural University, Thrissur, Kerala during *rabi*, 2017. Experiment was laid out in randomised block design with two factors (hydrogel and mulching) and an extra treatment (control). Both factors having three levels each. Three levels of hydrogel H₁ – 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂ – 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ and H₃ – 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and three types of mulch M₁ – rice straw mulch, M₂ – rice husk mulch, M₃ – Coirpith compost mulch were used in the experiment. Straw mulch and rice husk mulch were applied @ 5 t ha⁻¹ and coirpith compost mulch was applied @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The treatment combinations were T₁ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₂ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₃ - 1.25 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + Coirpith compost mulch, T₄ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₅ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₆ - 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + coirpith compost mulch, T₇ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice straw mulch, T₈ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + rice husk mulch, T₉ - 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel + coirpith compost mulch, T₁₀ - control (without hydrogel and mulch). The observations made on growth and growth attributes are like plant height at 30 and 60 DAS, NL and LA at 30, 60 and 90 DAS, DMP at 30, 60, 90 DAS and harvest stage and root volume at harvest stage. The recorded data was analysed statistically.

Results and Discussion**Plant height**

The plant height was significantly influenced by levels of hydrogel and types of mulch (Table 1). At 30 DAS, the maximum plant height was recorded in treatments in which hydrogel was applied @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (38.49 cm) which was superior to other two levels of hydrogel. At 60 DAS the hydrogel effect on plant height was not significant. Among the types of mulch, rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ observed maximum plant height at 30 DAS (39.76 cm) and 60 DAS (206.90 cm) and was significantly superior to other types of mulch. Interactions between hydrogel and mulch showed significant results on plant height at 30 DAS and it was non-significant at 60 DAS. At 30 DAS maximum plant height was noticed with interaction of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (41.16 cm). Comparing control with other treatments, minimum plant height was noticed in control and all the treatments were significantly superior to control at 30 and 60 DAS. After 60 DAS there was no substantial change was noticed in plant height because of development of tassel. The higher plant height in maize may be because of higher moisture retaining ability of hydrogel and reduced evaporation by rice straw mulch which leads to increase the nutrients availability to the plants and ultimately leading to increased plant height. Increased plant

height due to hydrogel application was also observed by the Kumari *et al.* (2017) and due to straw mulch application was reported by Uwah and Iwo (2011).

Number of leaves (NL) plant⁻¹

The impact of hydrogel on NL plant⁻¹ (Table 1) was found to be not significant at 30, 60 and 90 DAS. Among the types of mulch, the observation on NL was significant at 60 and 90 DAS only. At 60 and 90 DAS the maximum NL was noticed in rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (14.31 and 10.71 respectively). Interaction effect of levels of hydrogel and types of mulch was not significant at all the stages under observation (30, 60 and 90 DAS). When compared the control with other treatments, total NL was found significant at 30 and 90 DAS. Control had lower NL than all other treatments and its combinations. Overall, it was noticed that the NL plant⁻¹ was improved up to 60 DAS and subsequently declined till harvest stage. Mulching with rice straw @ 5 t ha⁻¹ retained the soil moisture for a longer period in the root zone of the crop may extend the senescence of lower leaves. This was similar with the outcomes of Uwah and Iwo (2011).

Leaf area (LA) plant⁻¹

It was observed that LA plant⁻¹ was significantly influenced by different levels of hydrogel, types of mulch and their interactions at 30, 60 and 90 DAS (Table 1). LA was maximum when hydrogel was applied @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ at all stages under observations (1196 cm², 3988 cm² and 3572 cm² respectively) and was significantly higher to other levels of hydrogel. Among types of mulch the maximum LA was noticed with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ at all the stages of observations (1327 cm², 4098 cm² and 4020 cm² respectively) which was significantly superior to rice husk and coirpith compost mulch. With regard to interaction between levels of hydrogel and types of mulch maximum LA was noticed with interaction of H₃M₁ (1454 cm², 4165 cm², 4071 cm² respectively) and was on par with H₂M₁ at 60 and 90 DAS and also with H₁M₁ at 90 DAS. When compared the control with other treatments, control recorded significantly lower LA at 30, 60 and 90 DAS. At harvest stage LA was not recorded as the entire plant was dried. Increased LA is a sign for increased photosynthetic capacity of the plant. It was observed that there was a decrease in the LA from 60 DAS to harvest stage but the rate of decrease was higher in control plot. It may be because of higher NL plant⁻¹ especially in case of rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ and hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ and 2.5 kg ha⁻¹. Decreased moisture content of plant resulted in decreased cell volume due to lower turgor pressure and consequent increase in solute concentration in cells. Hydrogel and rice straw mulch may increase the pressure potential of the cells by maintaining adequate quantity of moisture as per plant requirement and result in increased the LA (Yazdani *et al.*, 2007).

Root volume at harvest

Among the levels of hydrogel, maximum root volume was recorded by hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (25.50 cm³) which was significantly superior to other levels of hydrogel (Table 2). Among the types of mulch, maximum root volume was recorded by rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (24.17 cm³) which was significantly superior to other types of mulch. With respect to interactions, H₂M₁ (27.50 cm³) recorded maximum root volume and was on par with interaction H₃M₁ and was significantly superior to all other combinations. When compared the control with other treatments, control recorded lower root volume than the other treatments. The percentage increase in root volume over control was 47.14 % in treatment with hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ and 39.47 % in rice straw mulch applied plots. The treatment combination H₂M₁ (58.68 %) showed significantly higher percentage increase in root volume over control followed by H₃M₁ (46.16 %). The increased root volume due to hydrogel and straw mulch application was due to increased accessibility of soil moisture

and nutrients for a long time and maintenance of soil temperature and aeration for better root growth near the root zone of the crop. Higher moisture content may cause the poor aeration and reduced root growth. This might be the reason for decreased root volume at higher level of hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹. Increased root growth due to hydrogel application was also noticed by Zhang *et al.* (2005) in maize.

Dry matter production (DMP)

The DMP shown significant difference among the levels of hydrogel only at 30, 60 DAS and at harvest stage but it was non-significant at 90 DAS (Table 2). Maximum DMP at 30 and 60 DAS was observed in hydrogel applied @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ (7.37 and 78.07 g plant⁻¹ respectively). But at harvest stage maximum DMP was recorded by the treatment where hydrogel was applied @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (297.06 g plant⁻¹) which was on par with hydrogel level @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹. Among the different types of mulch, maximum DMP was observed at all stages in the treatment where rice straw was applied @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (8.39, 86.12, 239.10 and 303.42 g plant⁻¹ respectively), which was significantly superior to rice husk and coirpith compost mulch. With regard to interactions between levels of hydrogel and types of mulch at 30 and 60 DAS maximum DMP was recorded where hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹ with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ was applied (9.97 and 95.14 g plant⁻¹ respectively) and was significantly superior to all other combinations. At 90 DAS, H₂M₁ (243.18 g plant⁻¹) recorded maximum DMP which was on par with the combinations of rice straw mulch with other levels of hydrogel and significantly superior to other combinations. At harvest H₂M₁ (320.58 g plant⁻¹) recorded maximum DMP which was on par with H₃M₁ and was significantly superior to all other combinations. All the treatments and their interactions were significantly superior over control. When comparing the DMP in control with other treatments, it was found that the DMP in treatments varies from 15.78 % to 51.38 % over control. When comparing the percentage increase in DMP over control with the main effects of treatments Hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (40.27 %) and rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (43.28 %) recorded higher values. With regard to interactions, maximum percentage of DMP over control was recorded in H₂M₁ (51.28 %) followed by H₃M₁ (43.58 %).

DMP is a sign of efficient use of resources. Dry matter accumulation of maize mainly from leaves, since photosynthesis mainly occurs in the maize leaves, and LA determines the yield of maize. Maize growth is depending up on the capacity of the plant canopy to absorb solar energy and translate it into dry matter (Gifford *et al.*, 1984). Total DMP plant⁻¹ increased from 30 DAS to harvest stage in all the treatments. The higher DMP was may be due to an higher LA and photosynthetic capacity. The increased DMP at harvest stage with the application of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ was due to retention of more number of healthy and turgid leaves in the plant compared to other levels of hydrogel. This was further supported by the root volume at harvest stage. The root volume at harvest stage indicated that application of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ may be the optimum dose as further increase in quantity of hydrogel reduced the root volume significantly which directly influence the uptake of water and nutrients and finally the growth and DMP. Moisture stress at different stages of the crop decreases the capability of protoplasm to carry the photosynthesis and translocation of photo assimilates and growth regulators which creates turbulences in nitrogen metabolism. This ultimately resulted in reduced turgor of leaves and decreased growth (Kramer, 1969).

Similarly, higher DMP due to hydrogel application was observed by Silberbush *et al.* (1993) in maize and Yazdani *et al.* (2007) in soybean and due to straw mulch application by Khan and Parvej (2010) in maize.

Table 1. Effect of hydrogel and mulching on plant height, NL and LA

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	NL plant ⁻¹	LA plant ⁻¹ (cm ²)
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Levels of hydrogel	30 DAS	60 DAS	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS
H ₁	36.61	195.89	9.04	14.02	10.27	1105	3834	3435
H ₂	38.49	198.79	9.00	13.84	10.13	1073	3899	3472
H ₃	37.13	198.85	8.89	14.13	10.09	1196	3988	3572
SEm (±)	0.451	3.575	0.249	0.184	0.292	23.82	30.47	43.57
CD (0.05)	0.948	NS	NS	NS	NS	50.05	64.01	91.54
Types of mulch								
M ₁	39.76	206.90	9.18	14.31	10.71	1327	4098	4020
M ₂	35.44	188.54	8.73	13.84	9.80	990	3767	3058
M ₃	37.03	198.09	9.02	13.84	9.98	1058	3856	3401
SEm (±)	0.451	3.575	0.249	0.184	0.292	23.82	30.47	43.57
CD (0.05)	0.948	7.511	NS	0.387	0.614	50.05	64.01	91.54
Interactions								
H ₁ M ₁	40.27	203.04	9.27	14.07	10.33	1227	4006	3971
H ₁ M ₂	34.25	186.19	8.60	13.87	10.13	1039	3614	3059
H ₁ M ₃	35.31	198.45	9.27	14.13	10.33	1048	3881	3274
H ₂ M ₁	41.16	209.19	9.40	14.33	11.20	1300	4122	4019
H ₂ M ₂	34.95	190.93	8.80	13.87	9.73	951	3758	3074
H ₂ M ₃	39.35	196.25	8.80	13.33	9.47	968	3817	3324
H ₃ M ₁	37.84	208.46	8.87	14.53	10.60	1454	4165	4071
H ₃ M ₂	37.11	188.51	8.80	13.80	9.53	978	3930	3040
H ₃ M ₃	36.43	199.57	9.00	14.07	10.13	1157	3870	3605
SEm (±)	0.782	6.192	0.432	0.319	0.506	41.26	52.77	75.47
CD (0.05)	1.643	NS	NS	NS	NS	86.68	110.87	158.56
Control vs other treatments								
Control	31.93	181.98	8.20	13.60	9.07	86	3409	2909
SEm (±)	0.583	4.615	0.322	0.238	0.377	30.75	39.33	56.25
CD (0.05)	1.224	9.697	0.676	NS	0.792	64.61	82.64	118.18

Note: H₁ - hydrogel @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂ - hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹,

H₃ - hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹, M₁ - rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹,

M₂ - rice husk mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹, M₃ - coirpith compost mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Table 2. Effect of hydrogel and mulching on DMP and root volume at harvest

Treatment	DMP plant ⁻¹ (g plant ⁻¹)					Root volume at harvest (cm ³)	% increase over control (Root volume at harvest)
	Levels of hydrogel	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	At harvest		
H ₁	6.86	67.87	205.56	267.49	26.31	20.44	17.95
H ₂	6.83	72.06	207.82	297.06	40.27	25.50	47.14
H ₃	7.37	78.07	208.01	278.13	31.34	21.33	23.08
SEm (±)	0.222	0.767	3.261	6.401		0.595	
CD (0.05)	0.466	1.612	NS	13.449		1.251	
M ₁	8.39	86.12	239.10	303.42	43.28	24.17	39.47
M ₂	5.98	65.75	185.03	271.58	28.24	21.89	26.31
M ₃	6.70	66.12	197.25	267.68	26.40	21.22	22.45
SEm (±)	0.222	0.767	3.261	6.401		0.595	
CD (0.05)	0.466	1.612	6.851	13.449		1.251	
H ₁ M ₁	8.20	81.09	235.48	285.64	34.88	19.67	13.50
H ₁ M ₂	6.03	61.02	188.65	245.19	15.78	20.67	19.27
H ₁ M ₃	6.36	61.51	192.54	271.65	28.28	21.00	21.18
H ₂ M ₁	7.01	82.14	243.18	320.58	51.38	27.50	58.68
H ₂ M ₂	6.88	67.97	173.87	302.45	42.82	25.00	44.26
H ₂ M ₃	6.61	66.05	206.39	268.16	26.63	24.00	38.49
H ₃ M ₁	9.97	95.14	238.63	304.06	43.58	25.33	46.16
H ₃ M ₂	5.02	68.27	192.57	267.11	26.13	20.00	15.41
H ₃ M ₃	7.12	70.79	192.82	263.23	24.30	18.67	7.73
SEm (±)	0.384	1.329	5.648	11.087		1.031	
CD (0.05)	0.807	2.792	11.866	23.294		2.167	
Control	4.46	57.50	142.15	211.77		17.33	
SEm (±)	0.286	0.990	4.210	8.264		0.769	

CD (0.05)	0.601	2.081	8.844	17.362	1.615
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Note: H₁ - hydrogel @ 1.25 kg ha⁻¹, H₂ - hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹,
H₃ - hydrogel @ 3.75 kg ha⁻¹, M₁ - rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹,
M₂ - rice husk mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹, M₃ - coirpith compost mulch @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Conclusion

From the above results it was concluded that application of hydrogel @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ in combination with rice straw mulch @ 5 t ha⁻¹ shown the optimum for the growth of maize crop in sandy soil and recorded the higher growth than the other treatments

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